

Behaviour of Electrolytes in Mixed Solvents. Part VII. Conductance of Barium Chloride and Bromide in Dioxane-Water Mixtures at 35°

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The conductance of the solutions of barium chloride and bromide in 10, 20, and 30% dioxane-water mixtures by weight has been measured at 35°. Adopting the method of Jenkin and Monk, the dissociation constants and diameters of the ion pairs, $BaCl^+$ and $BaBr^+$, have been computed.

The conductance of the solutions of barium chloride and barium bromide in 10, 20, and 30% dioxane-water mixtures has been measured at 35°. This study has been undertaken with a view to ascertaining the effect of the solvent composition on the diameter of the ion pair $BaCl^+$ and $BaBr^+$. The dissociation constants of the ion pairs K_{BaCl^+} and K_{BaBr^+} required for calculating the diameter of the ion pairs by Bjerrum's method have also been calculated.

EXPERIMENTAL

$BaCl_2$ used was of B. D. H. 'AnalaR' quality, whereas $BaBr_2$ was of E. P. E. Merck variety. Both the samples were analysed for Ba^{2+} content by standard methods (Vogel, "Text Book of Quantitative Analysis", p.566). Preparations of the solvents, solutions, and conductance measurements at 35° have been reported earlier (this *Journal*, 1959, 39, 761).

TABLE I

Conc.	Conductance of barium chloride (ohm^{-1}) in			Conductance of barium bromide (ohm^{-1}) in		
	10% dioxane.	20% dioxane.	30% dioxane.	10% dioxane.	20% dioxane.	30% dioxane.
0.020	122.18	114.00	88.67	133.33	120.46	98.38
0.018	124.85	114.50	89.95	135.71	120.46	99.40
0.016	125.17	115.70	90.83	138.97	123.33	100.95
0.014	125.83	116.38	91.94	140.06	125.09	101.75
0.012	126.89	117.88	93.71	143.58	127.00	103.99
0.010	128.02	120.11	95.22	147.33	128.47	105.93
0.008	130.63	123.40	97.60	150.71	129.00	107.08
0.006	132.61	124.13	99.40	152.85	131.11	109.00
0.004	136.49	127.44	101.80	155.92	134.83	112.06
0.002	148.40	140.40	116.20	165.50	150.00	126.25

Conc. in equiv/litre.

DISCUSSION

Righellato and Davies (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, 26, 592) have pointed out that in case of mono-bivalent electrolytes equilibria of the type:

TABLE II

*Conc.	Barium chloride.				Barium bromide.					
	10% Dioxane, α $K \times 10^3$.	20% Dioxane, α $K \times 10^3$.	30% Dioxane, α $K \times 10^3$.	10% Dioxane, α $K \times 10^3$.	20% Dioxane, α $K \times 10^3$.	30% Dioxane, α $K \times 10^3$.	10% Dioxane, α $K \times 10^3$.	20% Dioxane, α $K \times 10^3$.	30% Dioxane, α $K \times 10^3$.	
0.020	0.9411	0.9298	0.8680	0.9561	0.9510	0.9542	18.20	11.42	0.9542	8.89
0.018	0.9358	0.9226	0.8889	0.9575	0.9608	0.9536	17.90	13.62	0.9536	8.53
0.016	0.9505	0.9208	0.8614	0.9627	0.9565	0.9664	21.93	11.70	0.9664	8.79
0.014	0.9465	0.9142	0.8820	0.9664	0.9601	0.9544	19.40	12.00	0.9544	8.02
0.012	0.9406	0.9192	0.8921	0.9777	0.9601	0.9514	22.27	12.39	0.9514	8.96
0.010	0.9378	0.9305	0.8959	0.9800	0.9645	0.9654	38.62	11.34	0.9654	9.30
0.008	0.9486	0.9386	0.9102	0.9974	0.9592	0.9629	-	0.18	0.9629	7.73
0.006	0.9511	0.9400	0.9127	0.960	0.9612	0.9647	-	7.53	0.9647	6.98
0.004	0.9740	0.9560	0.9187	0.919	0.9702	0.9709	-	7.65	0.9709	6.03
Mean										
$K \times 10^3$	10.35	5.71	2.73	23.06	10.76	8.20				
Diameter										
of the ion pair	1.12 Å	1.20 Å	1.23 Å	1.428 Å	1.497 Å	1.690 Å				

*Conc. in equiv./litre.

exist; the dissociation constant K for MA^- is

$$K = \frac{[M^+][A^{s-}]}{[MA^-]} \times \frac{f_{M^+} \times f_{A^{s-}}}{f_{MA^-}}$$

Assuming similar behaviour to exist in case of bi-monovalent electrolytes, $BaCl_2$ and $BaBr_2$,

$$K_{BaCl^+} = \frac{[Ba^{2+}][Cl^-]}{[BaCl^+]} \times \frac{f_{Ba^{2+}} \times f_{Cl^-}}{f_{BaCl^+}}$$

$$K_{BaBr^+} = \frac{[Ba^{2+}][Br^-]}{[BaBr^+]} \times \frac{f_{Ba^{2+}} \times f_{Br^-}}{f_{BaBr^+}}$$

where f represents the activity coefficients of the corresponding ions and the square bracket indicates the molar concentration.

Following the method of calculation by Jenkin and Monk, the values of ' α ' and the dissociation constants K_{BaCl^+} and K_{BaBr^+} of the electrolytes for each concentrations at different solvent compositions are calculated. The method of calculation has been reported earlier (*loc. cit.*).

The conductance data for $BaCl_2$ and $BaBr_2$ have been recorded in Table I. The calculated values of ' α ', the dissociation constant K , and the diameter of the ion pairs $BaCl^+$ and $BaBr^+$ have been tabulated in Table II. So far as the diameters of the ion pairs are concerned, it can be stated that the diameter of the ion pair $BaCl^+$ is unaffected up to 30% solvent composition, whereas that for $BaBr^+$ is so only up to 20% by composition.

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